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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 4

Pages: 332-338

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2669

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14259852

Manuscript Accepted: 09-01-2024

The Online Learning and Communicative Ability of the College Student

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to know the Impact of online learning when it comes to communicative ability, which consists of four aspects: pragmatic ability, socio-linguistic ability, theoretical ability, and discourse ability of Education students. This research is a quantitative and simple random sampling in which the researchers are free to take one hundred (100) respondents in the course of education from a private school in Bocaue, Bulacan. The researchers used the statistical method of linear regression to answer the problems. Based on the data results, students have a positive view of education regarding online learning. Self-motivation and teacher-student interaction have a significant impact on students' communicative ability in education. This overall study shows that online learning impacts the formation and growth of the communicative ability of Education students. The researchers believe that more attention needs to be paid to more interaction between students and their teachers. For online learning to flow smoothly, it is also important to have proper online learning equipment and a comfortable environment for students to learn fully.

Keywords: *impact, online learning, communicative competence, pragmatic competence, sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, discursive competence*

Introduction

It has been more than two years since the new way of learning, online learning, started. The spread of the COVID-19 virus was the reason for this change. Different learning methods have become a bridge, including modular and online learning, that requires the use of modern technologies that play a big role in implementing online learning and ensuring the learning of each student, especially in college.

According to Northenor (2020), the negative effects of online learning can be seen in its technical use. These effects include how technology is not always efficient, making it difficult for students to understand the concepts being taught. Online learning can cause social isolation and can cause unnecessary communication skills. The influential implications of online school are easy for students to use within the school.

Many things have been affected by the pandemic, such as the education sector. The government had a proposal to ban those under the age of twenty-one (21) and those over the age of sixty (60) from going out. A large percentage of them are students. That's why the government has implemented and proposed in the education sector Department of Education and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to have distance learning or learning methods, online, blended, and modular. Students will learn through gadgets, televisions, modules, and other learning tools.

That is why this research was conducted to determine the importance of the communicative ability to Educate students and wanted to know what challenges Education students face in online learning where it contains the challenge when it comes to technology and the challenge when it comes to telecommunications. I also wanted to assess the possible impact of online learning on the communicative ability of students in Education, whether it has a positive or negative result regarding their students' communicative ability.

This study will be the key to knowing what should be paid more attention to when it comes to online learning. For students it will help them develop their communicative ability. Teachers' minds will be opened to how they can improve and be active in the online learning class in shaping students' communicative ability. For parents who can see the challenges their child faces in online learning. And for the administration, that will be the key to adjusting their system for the development, improvement, and improvement of the school and the students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of online learning on the communicative ability of College Education students. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How does online learning affect the communicative ability of Education students in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 self-motivation;
 - 1.2 interaction with the Teacher and classmates;
 - 1.3 access equipment (internet connection, devices/gadgets); and
 - 1.4 environment?
2. What is the impact of online learning on the communicative ability of Education students in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 pragmatic ability;
 - 2.2 socio-linguistic competence;

- 2.3 strategic competence; and
- 2.4 discourse ability?
- 3. What is the implication of communicative competence in online learning of educational students in terms of the following:
 - 2.3 strategic competence; and
 - 2.4 discourse ability?

Methodology

This section of the research aims to know the used method of data collection, the method of selecting the respondent, and the research instrument, as well as the design used in the research.

Research Design

This type of research is quantitative because the questionnaires used aim to gather data regarding the Impact of Online learning on the communicative ability of college students. It used a descriptive-causal method that aims to find out the effect of Online learning on the communicative ability of students in education. Causal inference is finding an association between two factors and determining whether this is likely to be causal. Establishing a causal relationship requires not only statistical evidence but also clinical knowledge. Once an association is established, non-causal explanations, including bias, chance, and confounding, must be considered (Rothman & Greenland, 2005). Hill (1965) provided a set of 'considerations for causations' that provide weight to a causal interpretation for the association, namely, strength, consistency, specificity, temporality, biological gradient, plausibility, coherence, experimental evidence, and analogy.

Participants

For the researchers to obtain data on the impact of online learning on the communicative ability of college students," simple random sampling (equality of opportunity to make samples) was used. The selected respondents in this analysis are students from the first year to the fourth year who are taking an Education course in a private school in Bocaue, Bulacan. Freely choose one hundred (100) students from different specializations and years in the Education course who can represent this study. The researchers gave an orientation to their chosen respondents to fully understand the questions stated in the questionnaire used in this research, even preserving their identity and the data that the researcher can obtain and how well respondents will provide data.

Instruments

The instrument the researchers use to collect data is a survey questionnaire or questionnaire. Where the respondents will only choose according to their experience or feel (Strongly agree, Agree, Strongly disagree, Disagree, or No comment) that will be applicable to the conduct. This type of data collection is research because the respondents conform to the set nature of the research. In this method, the respondents' answers were conveyed quickly to the researchers.

Procedure

To gather the necessary information and data for the study, the researchers followed a series of well-structured steps. First, they conducted a thorough review to fully understand the scope and possibilities of the study, ensuring that the data collected would meet high-quality standards. A questionnaire was employed as the primary data collection tool, providing a user-friendly approach for both the researchers and respondents. To facilitate open and honest responses, a brief orientation was conducted with Education students, where the researchers emphasized the confidentiality of the data being collected. This helped create an environment where respondents could express themselves freely. The data collection process took place over several months, beginning in May 2022. Using Google Forms to distribute the questionnaire further streamlined the process, making it easier for the researchers to gather the necessary information efficiently.

Data Analysis

This research employed statistical methods to address the problems under investigation. To obtain specific insights from the selected respondents, the weighted mean was calculated, which allowed the researchers to determine how many respondents held a positive view regarding the presentation of the problem. In addition to this, linear regression analysis was conducted to assess whether the factors associated with the independent variable had any significant effects within the context of the study. These statistical tools provided a clear and quantitative means of understanding the respondents' perspectives and the relationships between variables in the research.

Results and Discussion

In this section, we can see the presentation of data and interpretation gathered by the researcher according to the Impact of Online Learning on the Communicative ability of Education students. These are based on each table.

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Entrance equipment	3.97	High

Environment	3.78	High
Self-motivation	3.84	High
Interaction with teacher and classmates	4.20	High
Total	3.97	High

Table 1 describes the situation of online learning students based on their access to equipment, environment, motivation, and interaction with the teacher and classmates. It has been shown that all such levels are described as high. Some (3.97) answered and said that Education students have enough equipment required for online admission, (3.78) those who have a good learning environment, (3.84) who have high self-motivation and (4.20) who answered that they have interaction with the teacher and classmates. Meanwhile, the highest mean was recorded in Interaction with the teacher and classmates with (4.20), and the environment got (3.78) the lowest mean in each said level.

According to Centeno-De Jesus (2020), technology and modern equipment (gadgets) play a big role in the set-up of education in our country to improve the condition and progress of students when it comes to Online study. It is also said that it is necessary to make the interaction between the teacher and the student more lively to have a smooth flow of learning and to shape the abilities of the students. This also includes making imperative the method of sharing the lesson with the students to focus and increase the motivation of the students in listening to the future discussion in the class.

Table 2. *Communicative Ability of Education students*

	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Pragmatic Ability	4.01	High
Socio-linguistic Competence	3.94	High
Strategic Ability	4.10	High
Discourse Ability	4.28	High
Total	4.08	High

The Communicative Ability of Education students is presented in Table 2. It is shown that all the levels mentioned are described as high. In discursive ability, there is a mean of 4.01, 3.94 for socio-linguistic ability, 4.10 for strategic, and 4.28 in discursive ability. It can be seen that the highest mean of students is in Discourse Ability, with 4.28, and the lowest was recorded in Socio-linguistic Ability, with 3.94. However, all students' communicative abilities can be described as "High," with a total mean of 4.08.

Michelle (2021) stated that online learning has a great impact on shaping the different abilities of students, especially their communication abilities. Michelle E. stated here that in online learning, it is necessary for students to be disciplined and organized. In addition to this, students also need to have a proper gadget and connection during class time to have a smooth flow of student learning. It adds that the lack of interaction of the student with his fellow students and his teacher in online learning does not shape the increase of his communicative ability.

Table 3. *Effect of online learning on the pragmatic ability of Education students*

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables	β	p	Verbal Interpretation
Pragmatic Ability	Equipment	.028	.748	No Significance
	Environment	.051	.607	No Significance
	Motivation	.274	.006	With Significance
	Interaction	.471	.000	With Significance

The effect of online learning on the pragmatic ability of Education students is shown in Table 3. It was proven that only self-motivation and interaction had an effect on the relationship with students' pragmatic ability because the calculated p-value was less than 0.05. Through this research it can be said that the students' pragmatic ability is affected by their motivation and interaction with the teacher and students in learning.

According to Felonia (2021), this study aims to determine the ability of teachers to teach different skills and equipment in teaching Filipino subjects during the pandemic. Teaching is an art because teachers are creative in their teaching to get the interest or interest of students and to learn, especially during the pandemic, through artistic means.

This study shows that the individual's ability to make, understand well, and have a meaningful sentence. This also agrees with the results of the data that only self-motivation and interaction with the teacher and student have a significant relationship regarding pragmatic ability.

Table 4. *Effect of online learning on Socio-linguistic ability of Education students*

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables	β	p	Verbal Interpretation
Socio-linguistic Competence	Equipment	.105	.307	No Significance
	Environment	.104	.362	No Significance
	Motivation	.303	.009	With Significance
	Interaction	.171	.106	No Significance

Table 4 shows the effect of online learning on the socio-linguistic ability of educational students. It emerged from this study that self-motivation affects the Socio-linguistic Competence of educational students. Because of this it can be said that the relationship of motivation with Socio-linguistic Competence has an effect. According to Ayon et al. (2019), in the study, "the proper use of the Filipino language in communication is important because it is used in our daily activities whether at work or at school. A lot can also happen if you don't know the proper use of words. That's why we must know how to use each word correctly, the tone and grammar in the Filipino language to better understand the message we want to convey".

This study agrees with the results of the data that only self-motivation has a significant relationship with sociolinguistic ability. Because through language we can properly convey and understand the message we want to convey regarding sociolinguistic ability.

Table 5. *Effect of online learning on the Strategic ability of Education students*

<i>Dependent Variables</i>	<i>Independent Variables</i>	β	<i>p</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Strategic Ability	Equipment	.113	.262	No Significance
	Environment	-.085	.448	No Significance
	Motivation	.371	.001	With Significance
	Interaction	.277	.008	With Significance

Table 5 shows the impact of online learning on student's strategic ability in education. In this study, input devices and environments can be said to have no effect when it comes to strategic ability. Self-motivation and interaction with the teacher and classmates directly affect the student's strategic ability. Because of this, it can be said that the relationship between motivation and interaction with strategic ability has an effect.

The model Anderson's Online Learning Model, explained by Picciano (2017), shows the interaction between teachers and students. This interaction occurs in the inquiry community using net-based synchronous and asynchronous activities. This includes cultivating social skills, collective learning, and building personal relationships with the participants. It is also said that the interaction of teachers and students is important in education, even in online learning, to develop or cultivate their skills when it comes to communicative ability that they can use in the future.

Table 6. *Effect of online learning on the Discourse ability of Education students*

<i>Dependent Variables</i>	<i>Independent Variables</i>	β	<i>p</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Discourse Ability	Equipment	.191	.067	No Significance
	Environment	-.095	.409	No Significance
	Motivation	.320	.006	With Significance
	Interaction	.237	.026	With Significance

In this part, Table 6 will show the effect of online learning on student's discourse ability in education. Entrance equipment and environment can be said to have no effect on discourse ability. Self-motivation and interaction with the teacher and classmates have an effect on the relationship with the student's discourse ability in education because the computed p-value is less than 0.05. According to Heramia (2017), "Language is what we use to communicate and understand each other. Communication is very important in one's life. In all areas of life, communication is necessary. This is why we understand each other and exchange different ideas, thoughts, and feelings with other people. Since we were in elementary school, we have been taught the different grammar and vocabulary of the Filipino language in school. Although we use it in our daily lives and communication, many Filipinos still do not know how to use it".

Conclusion

Based on the data gathered, the following conclusions were drawn. First, online learning encompasses various factors, including access to equipment, learning environment, motivation, and interaction with teachers and classmates, which can either facilitate or hinder the learning process. Despite these challenges, it was found that students adapted well to online learning when the pandemic began. Furthermore, the components of communicative ability—pragmatic, sociolinguistic, strategic, and discursive abilities—were shown to play a crucial role in enhancing students' communication skills, particularly in Education programs. The study also revealed that the factors influencing online learning and the components of communicative ability were well-developed, indicating that online learning did not impede the development of students' discourse skills. Specifically, the study demonstrated that online learning had a positive effect on students' pragmatic, strategic, and discursive abilities, which were linked to self-motivation and interaction with teachers and peers. However, only self-motivation significantly impacted sociolinguistic ability. Overall, the findings suggest that education students continued to enhance their discourse and communication skills despite the challenges of the pandemic, showing that online learning did not hinder their growth as future educators.

The study also presented several recommendations to improve the communicative abilities of students engaged in online learning. Teachers should employ diverse and appropriate strategies to better cultivate students' communicative skills, as their role is critical in student development. Additionally, educators are encouraged to be more creative in an online setup to maintain student engagement and interest, which is vital for developing various skills. It was suggested that future research could focus on outputs such as interviews, documentaries, and inquiries to demonstrate the effectiveness of online learning in enhancing students' communicative abilities. This research is particularly recommended for aspiring Filipino subject teachers as a guide for the proper use of language within sentences

and the development of strategic communication skills. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of self-motivation, along with the support from parents and the community, in encouraging student participation in class. Lastly, students should be provided with adequate equipment and a conducive environment for online learning to further enhance their communicative abilities.

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